

Qualitative Interviews with Publishers & Editors

Introduction/Briefing

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview. Your time and insights are greatly appreciated and will play a crucial role in helping us identify key barriers in Open Access publishing.

This interview is part of the IDAHO project, whose ultimate goal is to identify, describe, and mitigate or eliminate the barriers that researchers with weak institutional ties face when trying to publish Open Access. In this regard, this round of interviews with editors and publishers aims to determine whether they (you) are aware of these challenges and to explore any strategies or efforts you may have in place to accommodate researchers with limited institutional support in OA publishing.

Also, I would like to remind you that for us the names of the journals you represent are not of importance and we have made a conscious effort to contact different types of journals in order to gain a overall picture of the publishing environment.

Do you have any questions as of now?

Introduction
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Could you tell us a little about your role and experience with the journal you edit (publisher, discipline, business model)? 2. How important is Open Access publishing for your journal? <p><i>Thank you for that, now I would like to transition to the main part of the conversation.</i></p>
General Awareness
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What role do you think scientific editors play in advancing open access publishing? 2. What are your values in the role of journal editor? 3. Does it align with the publisher values set? 4. How would you describe your awareness of the barriers faced by researchers that have a weak or no affiliation through an organization, (we also call these weakly affiliated researchers and they include people such as: refugee scientists, retired researcher, independent researcher, NGO researcher) when they try to publish OA? 5. What do you see as the biggest challenges these researchers face when trying to publish OA?
Barriers

1. We had a look at your journal website and found that your journal...
 1. offers APC waivers → *Are weakly affiliated researcher eligible to apply?*
 1. *Are the terms of the waiver restricted by location?*
 1. *Could independent researchers from Germany apply?*
 2. does not offer APC waivers → *why is this the case?*
2. In what ways can the working language of your journal pose a barrier to researchers who wish to publish at your journal?
 1. Does your journal offer editorial editing services to improve language of a manuscript?
 1. If yes, is it paid?
 2. Do you think a language of submission system may pose an extra hurdler to potential authors? If so, how?
3. How might geolocation of the researcher play a role in publishing in your journal?
 1. *sanctions, Censorship and Content Restrictions, swift payment accessibility, etc.*
4. Are you aware of negative perceptions of your journal because it is open access?
5. Based on what issues do researchers reach out to you in the submission, review, and publication process? (Technical barriers - pre-registered databases of affiliations)
 1. *If yes, what about specifically weakly affiliated researchers?*

Editorial and Peer Review Considerations

1. How does your journal ensure **equitable/equal** treatment of submissions and peer review from researchers without strong institutional affiliations?
 1. Are there any initiatives to train editors and reviewers to recognize and mitigate biases?

Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) Policies

1. Has your journal developed an actionable Diversity, Equity & Inclusion plan to address barriers in scholarly publishing?
 1. *If yes → Is it focused on diversification among editors, reviewers, or specifically on the diversification of authors representation?*
 2. *If yes → Are weakly-affiliated researchers (as a group or independent researcher with no affiliation, or an affiliation different than a research institution/university) recognized in this plan/policy?*

If not → What is the reason for not having such a policy/plan?

1. Does your journal collect demographic information on your authors?
 1. *If yes, what information is being collected*
 1. *(location, institution, gender, race, age, etc.)*
 2. *Do you use this information for analysis to further diversify author portfolios?*
2. What other concrete steps has your journal taken (or does it plan to take) to reduce publication barriers for researchers with weak institutional ties?
3. How do you try and reach new authors for your journal?
 1. Which types of authors do you try to reach?
 1. How do you compile these lists of potential authors?
 2. What type of marketing strategies do you employ?
 3. To what degree do you think marketing is successful?

Outlook and perspectives

1. In your experience, what additional resources or changes would help authors navigate the open access publishing process more effectively?
1. Are there similar journals in the same field as yours that are closed access?
 2. What are your needs to improve the diversity of your journal's authors?